

Level of job readiness of St. Dominic College of Asia grade 12 techvoc cookery students to face the working industry

Gerald Dine Bernardino II¹, Eleonor D. Aguilando^{2*}

¹Hospitality Management Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

²School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: eaquilando@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Technical Vocational in Commercial Cooking of St. Dominic College of Asia is designed to produce competent cookery students who are expected to be employed or self-employed. This study aimed to assess the level of Grade 12 Technical Vocational Cookery students in terms of skills and knowledge if they are equipped with essential competencies and skills necessary for employment. The research was conducted using quantitative research study by using descriptive method with 42 participants answered the survey. Statistical treatment was utilized in the analysis of data collected from the survey. The study's findings demonstrate that TechVoc Education's curriculum is competent in terms of content as well as includes the skill elements required to succeed in the workplace. TechVoc particularly those who are handling the commercial cooking program provides the necessary skills and competencies to Grade 12 students that focuses in the three assessment levels of competencies in: (a) Prepare and cook hot meals; (b) Prepare cold meals; and (c) Prepare sweets. Various methods of food preparation and presentation are taught to students based on industry norms, such as how to receive, store, and manage kitchen supplies. The training also improves students' abilities to organize, prep, cook, and serve a variety of cuisines. Respondents learned cooking skills in different cooking methods and preparation. The respondents believed that the TechVoc program was highly valuable and that they are confident to face the working industry with competitive value.

Keywords: Job readiness; technical vocational education; cookery; working industry.

To cite this article:

Bernardino II, G. D., & Aguilando, E. D. (2021). Level of job readiness of St. Dominic College of Asia grade 12 techvoc cookery students to face the working industry. *Hospitalite*, 5, 32-43.

Introduction

Agri-Fishery Arts, Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Information and Communication Technology represent the four components of the K–12 Basic Education Program (BEP), and together they are referred to as Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) (Luistro, 2012). Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) shows the training of individuals for the incoming technology development of a nation to right the skill necessary for employment. Technical and vocational education is widely available today, and as a result, it contributes significantly to the welfare of the country. Short courses in welding and fabrication, mechanical/automotive technology, electrical/electronic technology, woodworking and construction technology, among others were included in the program. Due to its peculiar nature, it also acts as a catalyst for national changes in the economy, society, and politics (Uwaifo, 2010).

Furthermore, having access to renewable skills is becoming more and more important for the future of the globe. Some established and underdeveloped countries are aware of the crucial role that TVE serves in equipping people with the necessary knowledge and skills, enabling them to actively engage in social, economic, and technical development activities (Idris & Mbudai, 2017). The trend of globalization, technological advancements, and a fierce growth competition brought on by economic policy are the main forces causing change in the workplace. These have significant implications for skill demand (UNESCO, 2009).

Thus, TVE is an approach for empowering students with the academic, employment, and knowledge needed to seek higher education, engage the workforce, and maintain learning (Brand et al., 2013). These program provide students of being competent because that is a requirement in today's workplace such as critical thinking, problem solving, and teamwork. By experiencing work, they have been learning about different careers and workplaces. It is about preparing students for their future careers (Alam, 2008).

In an effort to determine the degree of capabilities, the author defines work preparedness as those fundamental abilities required for obtaining, maintaining, and excelling in a job and can be broken down into three different groups: Basic Academic Skills, Higher-Order Thinking Skills, and Personal Qualities (Robinson, 2000). In more contemporary usage, the phrase is frequently used to indicate the groundwork or fundamental abilities from which an individual has to develop job-specific skills, such as creating a sales report (Saterfiel & Mclarty, 1995). The term additionally relates to the skills necessary to obtain and maintain a job. According to Zinser (2003, 2015), career and employability abilities comprise things like managing resources, interpersonal and communication skills, teamwork, problem-solving, and looking and maintaining a job. Job equipped skills are further characterized as a compilation of accomplishments, comprehensions, and character traits that increase an individual's likelihood of finding employment and accomplishment in their desired professions (Tran, 2016). Buck and Barrick (1987) gave a more detailed characterization of the capabilities needed for work preparedness. The following competency areas were used to categorize job preparation skills: personal values, problem-solving and decision-making abilities, interpersonal relationships, communication abilities, task-related abilities, maturity, health and safety practices, and dedication to job. In general, students need professional abilities to equip themselves to fulfill the requirements of numerous occupations after graduation (Shafie & Nayan, 2010).

Employers today have to cope with finding qualified employees who show fundamental academic skills like reading, writing, science, mathematics, oral communication, and listening along with higher order thinking abilities like comprehension, logic, creativity, choice-making, and problem-solving. Additionally, they are seeking workers with a variety of personal qualities, such as accountability, self-assurance, self-control, social skill, honesty, integrity, adaptability and flexibility, punctuality and efficiency, self-direction, a positive attitude at work, grooming, cooperation, self-motivation, and self-management. The majority of current alumni, however, are not aware of this phenomenon, in which students occasionally fail to draw a line within what they learn in class and the actual industry they will eventually join. In order for these undergraduates to succeed in their chosen sector after graduation, it is the responsibility of the instructors to guarantee that they have the necessary job preparation skills (Wiebe et al., 2018).

Nowadays, there are not many job opportunities available, so the Department of Education is reviving its resources to guide the next generation and train them expertly as future chefs. It involves developing the abilities that students can use to meet their own and others' everyday demands. It aims to give learners the knowledge, attitude, values, and abilities necessary for cooking. These technical abilities are assessed and now subject to teacher evaluation in our K-12 Curriculum. This curriculum is currently being implemented in our nation to assist all students in learning a certain skill.

This research also focuses on the different activities that will assess the level of Grade 12 Technical Vocational Cookery students in terms of skills and knowledge if they are equipped with essential competencies and skills necessary for employment. To illustrate the ideas and basic competencies outlined by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) training standards for commercial cooking, a variety of engaging and appropriate tasks and opportunities are offered (TESDA, 2010).

St. Dominic College of Asia's curriculum in Technical Vocational – Home Economics strand in Commercial Cooking is aligned with TESDA's training program wherein various methods of food preparing and presenting are taught to students based on industry norms, such as how to receive, store, and manage kitchen supplies. The training also improves students' abilities to organize, prep, cook, and serve a variety of cuisines. They learn how to prepare and/or cook a variety of foods, including sandwiches, eggs, appetizers, salads, veggies, and desserts. Direct observation, simulations, real-world examples, and oral and written tests are used to do this. Their performance and learning outcomes will evaluate if they become globally competitive and will have opportunities for better career employment in a rapidly and increasingly globalized environment.

Related Studies

The study of Hagos and Dejarme (2008) suggested that all together for schools and colleges to adapt to new developments, they should keep at pace with the beat of cultural changes and mechanical advancement. The schools of today ought to take part in the instructive and social upset. Along these lines, the educational plan in the Philippine school today must be equipped to the fast cultural changes and the new obligations regarding the new type of Filipinos (Mondoñedo, 2019). The three most significant parts of society that give direct contribution to the improvement of the educational program are the academe (foundations), the legislature, and the enterprises (both open and privately owned businesses).

Garduque (2012) claimed in their study that knowing theories alone are insufficient and that people also need to possess practical skills. These are technical skills and programs for a living that could assist students and graduates in becoming future skilled employees (as cited in Carale, 2019). Tullao et al. (2015) emphasized different perspectives and views on the readiness of professionals to compete internationally. To start with, the office of Filipinos to work abroad and contend with outside experts with comparative aptitudes and skill. Second, the capacity of experts to rival remote experts entering the neighbourhood economy. The third point of view is centred around the capacity of experts to fulfil the guidelines and human asset prerequisites of outside ventures just as local organizations in their utilization of different administrations.

The first and second viewpoints are preceded by a discussion on the necessity to strengthen human resources (HR) in order to prepare Filipino professionals for remote challenge both domestically and overseas in a shifting global market for services. Another point of view, on the other hand, prepares experts by emphasizing the importance of human capital as a key component of extending the economic framework. Due to the nature of professional services, such a partnership will have the effect of boosting local specialists' status both domestically and internationally. It will also make the Philippines an encouraging location for international investment. In essence, the nation builds a strong human resource structure in addition to protecting its specialists from external threats.

According to the technical teachers' perceptions in Adamawa State, Nigeria, there are several aspects that influence the learner's academic and technical skill (Kumazhege & Egunsola, 2014). They advocate for their government to build a teacher preparation program for technical teachers and provide their pupils with adequate facilities and laboratories. Based on the research, it is no longer necessary for typical high school students to be able to grasp and carry out specific job-related tasks. They must now be able to put things into perspective and use fundamental abilities like reading, writing, and math to solve difficulties at work (Clagett, 1997; Lynch, 2000). Hyslop (2008) reaffirmed that the same tasks must help students earn certifications for being ready for the workforce. They believed that this could only happen

through assisting students in applying their knowledge through planning and assessment, as well as by putting them in touch with industries and businesses. By assuring workplace success, Career Technical Education (CTE) in comprehensive high schools offers the potential and capacity to enhance the value of the high school credential. Some people believe comprehensive high schools, nevertheless, are unable to offer smooth transitions from education to the workplace. It is critical to comprehend these programs' histories and purposes for CTE programming, even if they are frequently reviewed and altered to accommodate a changing workplace (Hall, 2010).

According to McGrath et al. (2006), the main goals of vocational education are to: (1) develop worthwhile values for daily personal and household life; (2) develop a wholesome personality and satisfying interpersonal relationships; and (3) identify student needs, interests, and abilities in relation to resources for the home and family to achieve the desired goals for home and family living.

According to a study conducted among students at a technical training facility in Malaysia, Bakar and Hanafi (2007) said that students naturally pick up employability skills during training and education, hence they cannot be taught. Additionally, students pursuing production technology and industrial electronics at a technical training center in Malaysia have developed a somewhat high level of employable skills over the course of their education and training. Students at this institution are prepared for the workplace of today, especially in fields that place a greater emphasis on technical and desirable abilities.

The effectiveness of any vocational, educational, or specialized course of instruction is determined by the ability of the instructor to teach, according to Fix et al. (2019) who underlined the significance of having trained professionals in the field of teaching. If something goes wrong at this stage, the entire building collapses. Therefore, vocational education is chosen, prepared for, and managed.

Carnevale et al. (2010) said that vocation status has become a key need for the K12 instruction network and the country on the loose. The undeniably serious worldwide economy causes it basic that more understudies to enter vocation handle that empower higher wages and more prominent potential for development, however establishments of advanced education and the business network have since a long time ago communicated worries about the deficiency of conventional secondary school instruction in getting ready understudies for the postsecondary instruction or preparing important to prevail in preparing students for the post-secondary education or training necessary to succeed in these careers.

Hirschi (2010) also noted that many of the qualities and skills of graduates are marketable in a journal of career assessment. This indicates that employers respect them. He or she can use the marketable skills for particular occupations. Employers will expect them to have the necessary personality and interpersonal abilities to fit in at work, as well as job-specific talents. The following are examples of job-specific skills: carpentry, sewing, electrical wiring, and bookkeeping. The ability to get along with others, work well in a team, manage time, respect diversity, plan tasks, and solve problems are examples of general abilities.

According to a study by Cook (2013), nations with a higher percentage of secondary school pupils enrolled in vocational education tend to have lower rates of youth unemployment. It is vital to remember that student involvement is a crucial component of education, even though this relationship cannot be overemphasized. Most important are their career and future aspirations. Education programs must be available to students of diverse skills and aptitudes in order to foster involvement, especially for those who have no intention of attending university.

Clear career pathways must be provided to support these programs. Technical programs, particularly those providing Technical Vocational Education Training (TVET), are highly correlated with labor demands in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines and high-demand job paths in several provinces and school boards. This strategy gives students choices that open up entry-level employment opportunities, college degrees, and advanced professional possibilities.

The majority of employability studies have focused on higher education; few, if any, have truly given secondary school employability much thought. However, it is expected of educational institutions to address the need for employability throughout all levels (McGrath et al., 2020). By emphasizing employable skills at the middle school level, this study fills a void. Graduates from this level of education should have a well-rounded development (Igbokwe, 2015); but there is still a lot to be desired. Despite teacher and student efforts in recent years, youngsters are leaving school functionally insufficiently literate to handle the rigors of daily life.

Additional research in Zimbabwe has linked graduates' lack of employable skills to deficiencies, such as a lack of preparation materials, large class sizes, inadequate learning spaces, a lack of mechanical cooperative energies, and insufficient educational opportunities in specialized instruction facilities, to name just a few (Woyo, 2013). This the truth is additionally caught in Bangladesh and Ghana where employable aptitudes among specialized alumni are fundamentally ascribed to the nonappearance of linkages among preparing and the universe of work (Dasmani, 2011; Islam & Mia, 2007). Therefore, in certain nations like Ghana conveyance of TVET programs is seen as not significant to the neighborhood financial condition given that it does not viably react to the requirements of the casual division just as a working showcase, along these lines maddening the issue of joblessness among graduates (Dyankov, 1996). Subsequently, a few nations in Africa dread to put resources into specialized instruction foreseeing that general training would be progressively adaptable, reasonable and equipped for reacting to financial and work power changes in the public arena (Lauglo & Lillis, 1988).

The preparedness of the schools in implementing the K to 12 Curriculum Program in terms of curriculum change, school plant and facilities, instructional materials, operations and administration; preparedness for instructors in terms of teaching skills, methods of instruction, utilization of instructional materials, and adjustments were examined in this study. More of the related studies were not directly focused on the level of job readiness of grade 12 St. Dominic College of Asia Technical Vocational cookery students to face the working industry in the kitchen but they are reflected the other variables within the study such as technical skills, job readiness / employability skills. The variables of the study were strengthened through the presentation of the literatures and studies from both foreign and local sources which were earlier presented.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized quantitative research study by using descriptive method as the basis for the design. It aims to collect information regarding the level of job readiness of grade 12 cookery students of St. Dominic College of Asia to face the working industry through the use of a Likert Scale.

Participants

This study involves a total of 42 Grade 12 Technical Vocational Cookery students of St. Dominic College of Asia. They were consisting of 27 males and 15 female students. The participants were identified through Purposive Sampling Technique. The following criteria helped in the selection of the participants:

1. The sample was selected from the list of registered technical vocational commercial cookery students.
2. The participants should have knowledge on technical vocational education, concepts, and training system.

Instrumentation

Likert Scale was utilized in gathering information on assessing the technical skills of Grade 12 Cookery students. The survey questions were questionnaires based on TESDA Training Regulations (Cookery NC II) promulgated last October 2014 that covers the three common competencies that grade 12 cookery students ought to possess for skills evaluation. Items were worded to reflect what respondents perceived about their technical skills in commercial cooking.

Each question is a Five-Point Likert Scale with responses ranging from:

- 1.0 – 2.5 – not ready; needs a lot of work
- 2.6 – 3.3 – not ready; needs some work
- 3.4 – 4.1 – ready but needs a few improvement
- 4.2 – 5.0 – ready go ahead

Data Collection and Analysis

The researchers asked permission from the department head to conduct a study on Grade 12 Technical Vocational Cookery students. Survey questionnaires were utilized to gather data. Confidentiality was given to assure cooperation and to avoid inhibitions from the respondents. The analysis and interpretation of data was facilitated through the use of statistical tools which include weighted mean. Data analysis was done using descriptive technique.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Mean, Frequency Count, and Average in Preparing and Cooking Hot Meals

Statements	Frequency	Interpretation
1. Gather, check tools and equipment needed	4.48	Ready go ahead
2. Clean and/or sanitize kitchen equipment and utensils*	4.52	Ready go ahead
3. Store and stack cleaned equipment and utensils	4.48	Ready go ahead
4. Follow cleaning schedules	4.48	Ready go ahead
5. Use appropriate chemicals and equipment in cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises, tools, and equipment*	4.60	Ready go ahead
6. Check, record and label supplies	4.24	Ready go ahead
7. Gather, identify and select ingredients as per required	4.50	Ready go ahead
8. Prepare ingredients and flavoring agents as per required menu items*	4.60	Ready go ahead
9. Select and assemble ingredients to produce varieties of soups, stocks, and sauces*	4.43	Ready go ahead
10. Select primary, secondary and portioned cuts of protein; pork, lamb, beef, veal, and seafood*	4.31	Ready go ahead
11. Identify and use appropriate cooking methods*	4.17	Ready but needs a few improvement
12. Organize and prepare food items according to menu requirements*	4.31	Ready go ahead
13. Cook menu items as required*	4.21	Ready go ahead
14. Arrange sauces and garnishes*	4.33	Ready go ahead
15. Plate and present food*	4.26	Ready go ahead
16. Select packaging materials for foodstuffs	4.02	Ready but needs a few improvement
17. Adapt appropriate packaging procedures*	4.02	Ready but needs a few improvement
18. Store food in appropriate condition*	4.12	Ready but needs a few improvement
19. Follow workplace safety and hygiene procedures*	4.26	Ready go ahead
20. Perform first aid procedure in the event of accident	4.07	Ready but needs a few improvement
Average	4.32	Ready go ahead

The table shows the distribution of statistics on respondents' evaluation in terms of cooking hot meals. The data shows that all of the respondents are in the ready go ahead level of readiness with the overall mean of 4.32. Of all measures of skills in preparing and cooking hot meals the respondent scored highest on in terms of using proper chemicals and equipment in cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises, tools and equipment, and preparing ingredients and flavoring agents as per required menu items with the score of 4.60. The lowest score of 4.02 was in the area of selecting packaging materials for foodstuffs and adapt appropriate packaging procedures. This is the area that needs greater emphasis by treating also as ingredient in food safety this will help trace and recall products faster and efficiently. It is important to choose the right packaging material depending on the food's content. The most effective protection and durability will be provided by using appropriate packaging.

Table 2. Mean, Frequency Count, and Average in Preparing and Cooking Hot Meals

Statements	Frequency	Interpretation
1. Clean and/or sanitize kitchen equipment and utensils*	4.38	Ready go ahead
2. Store and stack cleaned equipment and utensils	4.10	Ready but needs a few improvement
3. Follow cleaning schedules	4.40	Ready go ahead
4. Use appropriate chemicals and equipment in cleaning and maintaining kitchen premises, tools and equipment*	4.52	Ready go ahead
5. Select and assemble tools and equipment*	4.43	Ready go ahead
6. Inspect tools and equipment*	4.48	Ready go ahead
7. Check, record and label supplies	4.02	Ready but needs a few improvement
8. Identify and select ingredients as per required menu items *	4.17	Ready but needs a few improvement
9. Prepare variety of sandwich types*	4.36	Ready go ahead
10. Select suitable bases from a range of bread type*	4.24	Ready go ahead
11. Prepare appetizers and salads with suitable sauces and dressings*	4.60	Ready go ahead
12. Utilize quality trimmings or other leftovers	4.64	Ready go ahead
13. Select and prepare variety of vegetables, fruits, and starch food according to recipes*	4.52	Ready go ahead
14. Select and prepare variety of cold dishes according to recipe requirements*	4.33	Ready go ahead
15. Identify and use appropriate cooking methods*	4.64	Ready go ahead
16. Organize and prepare food items according to menu requirements*	4.45	Ready go ahead
17. Plate and present food*	4.60	Ready go ahead
18. Select packaging materials for foodstuffs	4.24	Ready go ahead
19. Adapt appropriate packaging procedures*	4.21	Ready go ahead
20. Store food in appropriate condition*	4.26	Ready go ahead
21. Minimize wastage through purchases*	4.50	Ready go ahead
22. Follow workplace safety and hygiene procedures*	4.64	Ready go ahead
23. Perform first aid procedures in the event of accident	4.31	Ready go ahead
24. Prepare reports	4.33	Ready go ahead
25. Coordinate end of service procedures	4.52	Ready go ahead
Average	4.40	Ready go ahead

In table 2 the respondents were also asked to rate the level of preparedness in terms of preparing cold meals. The average mean score of 4.40 indicate that students were all well prepared with the highest score of 4.64 in terms of a) Utilizing quality trimmings or other leftovers, b) Identifying and using appropriate cooking methods, and c) Following workplace safety and hygiene procedures. The lowest mean score of 4.02 was in the area of checking, recording, and labeling supplies. This means to make constant follow-up and repetition in this area.

Table 3. Mean, Frequency Count, and Average in Preparing Sweets

Statements	Frequency	Interpretation
1. Select and use chemicals and clean potable water for cleaning and/or sanitizing kitchen equipment, utensils, and working surfaces according to manufacturer’s instructions	4.36	Ready go ahead
2. Store or stack clean equipment, supplies and utensils safely in the designated place in accordance with manufacturer’s instructions	4.33	Ready go ahead
3. Assemble and disassemble cleaning equipment safely	4.38	Ready go ahead
4. Follow cleaning schedules based on enterprise procedures	4.36	Ready go ahead
5. Clean and/or sanitize walls, floors, shelves, and working surfaces without causing damage to health or property	4.31	Ready go ahead
6. Follow first aid procedures if an accident happens	4.31	Ready go ahead
7. Sort and dispose waste according to sanitary regulations, enterprise practices and standard procedures*	4.40	Ready go ahead
8. Dispose cleaning chemicals safely according to standard procedures*	4.19	Ready but needs a few improvement
9. Demonstrate sanitizing procedures and techniques*	4.31	Ready go ahead
10. Use ingredients and flavoring agents according to standard recipes defined by the enterprise	4.36	Ready go ahead
11. Identify ingredients according to standard recipes, recipe card, or enterprise requirements	4.26	Ready go ahead
12. Assemble ingredients according to quantity, type, and quality required	4.24	Ready go ahead
13. Prepare ingredients based on the required form and time frame	4.19	Ready but needs a few improvement
14. Select, measure and weigh ingredients according to recipe requirements	4.24	Ready go ahead
15. Thaw frozen ingredients following enterprise procedures	4.12	Ready but needs a few improvement
16. Observe factors in plating dishes in presenting cold dessert	4.19	Ready but needs a few improvement
17. Produce a variety of hot, cold, and frozen desserts, appropriate for a variety of menus*	4.14	Ready but needs a few improvement
18. Produce sweet sauces to a desired consistency and flavor*	4.19	Ready but needs a few improvement
19. Taste prepare desserts and sweets in accordance with the required taste	4.24	Ready go ahead
20. Present dessert hygienically, logically, and sequentially within the required timeframe, and decorate creatively	4.19	Ready but needs a few improvement
21. Plate and portion desserts according to enterprise standards	4.10	Ready but needs a few improvement
22. Store dessert at the appropriate temperature and correct conditions to maintain quality, freshness, and customer appeal	4.62	Ready go ahead
23. Select and use suitable packaging to preserve taste, appearance, and tasting characteristics	4.45	Ready go ahead
24. Select quality of packaging materials in accordance with enterprise standards	4.29	Ready go ahead
25. Observe environmental requirements for food packaging	4.29	Ready go ahead
26. Package food in compliance with sanitary occupational health and safety and local health regulations requirements	4.07	Ready but needs a few improvement
27. Label food according to industry standards	4.50	Ready go ahead
Average	4.28	Ready go ahead

In Table 3 the same procedure has been applied and the results show the average mean score of 4.28 in the area of preparing sweets. The item “Store dessert at the appropriate temperature and correct conditions to maintain quality, freshness and customer appeal” had the highest mean score of 4.62. The lowest score falls in the area “Package food in compliance with sanitary occupational health and safety and local health regulations requirements” with a mean score of 4.07. In this area the procedures in dealing with package food must be followed in accordance with the sanitary and occupational health and safety department. The overall mean of the respondents can be concluded that they felt that their curriculum was worthwhile and that the quality of their education as a whole satisfied them. Additionally, they were sufficiently equipped for the future in terms of level of job readiness to face the working industry (Rahman, 2010).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of job readiness of St. Dominic College of Asia Grade 12 TechVoc cookery student to face the working industry. The respondents generally have the knowledge and training necessary to succeed. By introducing the students to workplace skills that are necessary for job preparedness, it also gets them ready for life in the workforce. Variables identified as possible predictors of job readiness were: (a) Prepare and cook hot meals; (b) Prepare cold meals; and (c) Prepare sweets.

The average mean to prepare and cook hot meals is 4.32 that is in the ready go ahead level of readiness, which is a clear manifestation of the effectiveness of its curriculum and its content. The respondents' analysis in terms of preparing cold meals was in a great extent also with average mean of 4.40. In Prepare Sweets category although the lowest from the three areas of competencies with the average mean of 4.28, still it is in the ready go ahead level of skills to face the working industry. From the three categories the Grade 12 students have the knowledge and applied skills critical for success in job readiness. The results showed the respondents possess the ability to adapt and sustain employment.

Grade 12 cookery students are in the ready go ahead level of skills to face the working industry in terms of the following skills: (a). Prepare and cook hot meals; (b) Prepare cold meals; (c) Prepare sweets. St. Dominic College of Asia's Technical Vocational Home Economics strand in commercial cooking has taught students acquire the employability skills for their employment. The skills required to face the working industry are integrated into the curriculum to ensure that grade 12 TechVoc cookery students have the skills needed for employment or relevant to what the industry requires.

Respondents have a thorough awareness of essential issues, skills, production principles, nutrition, safety, and quality services. The assessment indicates that Grade 12 TechVoc Cookery students learned and possessed the right knowledge and skills in performing the task and the trainer were capable in teaching the competencies covered in competency based curriculum / assessment of St. Dominic College of Asia in commercial cooking.

From the drawn conclusions, the following recommendations are listed below:

1. Satisfactory time ought to be allotted to subjects that require commonsense preparing.
2. Re-preparing of educators ought to be sorted out so as to refresh their insight and aptitudes.
3. Students should be given the opportunity to interact with expert and professionals in their field of studies.
4. Establish standards of excellence or mastery, hold all students to proficiency levels in accordance with those standards, and personalize the learning experience by giving each student a course of study that is specific to his or her learning needs and interests while aiming toward attaining the minimum requirements.
5. Similar research should be conducted using the same tools and methods, but in other settings with larger sample sizes.

References

- Alam, G. (2008). The role of technical and vocational education in the national development of Bangladesh. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 9(1), 25-44. https://www.ijwil.org/files/APJCE_09_1_25_44.pdf
- Bakar, A. R., & Hanafi, I. (2007). Assessing employability skills of technical-vocational students in Malaysia. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(4), 202-207.

- Brand, B., Valent, A., & Browning, A. (2013). *How career and technical education can help students be college and career ready: A primer*. College and Career Readiness and Success Center. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED555696.pdf>
- Buck, L. L., & Barrick, R. K. (1987). They're trained, but are they employable? *Vocational Education Journal*, 62(5), 29-31.
- Carale, D. R. T. (2019). Remediation activities: An intervention to improve senior high school performance in technical vocational education track. In P. M. Jayaweera (Ed.), *Conference proceedings of the Asia international conference on multidisciplinary research* (Vol. 1, pp. 5-13).
- Carnevale, A. P., Smith, N., & Strohl, J. (2010). *Help wanted: Projections of job and education requirements through 2018*. Lumina Foundation.
- Claggett, C. A. (1997). *Workforce skills needed by today's employers*. Market Analysis MA98-5. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED413949.pdf>
- Cook, W. (2013). *Vocational education in English schools: Protecting options for pre-16 pupils*. Institute for Public Policy Research. <https://www.voced.edu.au/content/ngv:56280>
- Dasmani, A. (2011). Challenges facing technical institute graduates in practical skills acquisition in the Upper East Region of Ghana. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 12(2), 67-77. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=be76adb72438540a9b0efc4061bd9bd09e8d50e7>
- Dyankov, A. (1996). *Current issues and trends in technical and vocational education*. Section for Technical and Vocational Education, UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000108579>
- Fix, G. M., Ritzen, H. T. M., Pieters, J. M., & Kuiper, W. A. J. M. (2019). Effective curricula for at-risk students in vocational education: a study of teachers' practice. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 11, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-018-0076-5>
- Garduque, N. S. (2012). *Teacher's performance in Benigno Ninoy Aquino High School in technology & livelihood vocational education as perceived by the students* (Unpublished master's thesis, Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College).
- Hagos, L. C., & Dejarne, E. G. (2008, November 19-21). *Enhancing curriculum in Philippine schools in response to global community challenges* [Paper presentation]. EDU-COM 2008 International Conference. Sustainability in Higher Education: Directions for Change, Edith Cowan University, Perth Western Australia. <https://ro.ecu.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1020&context=ceducom>
- Hall, V. L. (2010). *Work readiness of career and technical education high school students* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia). https://getd.libs.uga.edu/pdfs/hall_valery_1_201012_edd.pdf
- Hirschi, A. (2010). The role of chance events in the school-to-work transition: The influence of demographic, personality and career development variables. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 77(1), 39-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2010.02.002>
- Hyslop, A. (2008). CTE's role in workforce readiness credentialing. *Techniques: Connecting Education and Careers (J1)*, 83(6), 40-43. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ809549.pdf>
- Idris, A., & Mbudai, Y. (2017). Technical and vocational education: Challenges towards youths empowerment in Kano State-Nigeria. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 9(1). <https://publisher.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/JTET/article/view/1281>
- Igbokwe, C. O. (2015). Recent curriculum reforms at the basic education level in Nigeria aimed at catching them young to create change. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 31-37. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-3-1-7>
- InWEnt, UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre, & The Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization Regional Centre for Vocational and Technical Education and Training. (2009). *Corporate HRD and skills development for employment: scope and strategies; Final report*. UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for Technical and Vocational Education and Training. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000186849>
- Islam, M. R., & Mia, A. (2007). The role of education for rural population transformation in Bangladesh. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 8(1), 1-21. https://www.ijwil.org/files/APJCE_08_1_1_21.pdf

- Kumazhege, S. Z., & Egunsola, A. O. E. (2014). Technical teachers' perception of factors affecting practical skill acquisition among technical college graduates in Adamawa State Nigeria. *Educational Research International*, 3(3), 95-101. [http://erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/Vol.3\(3\)/ERInt.2014\(3.3-11\).pdf](http://erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/Vol.3(3)/ERInt.2014(3.3-11).pdf)
- Lauglo, J., & Lillis, K. (1988). *Vocationalizing education: An international perspective*. Pergamon Press.
- Luistro, A. A. (2012, July 10). *Guidelines on the implementation of Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program (STVEP) and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) curriculum*. Department of Education. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/DO_s2012_67.pdf
- Lynch, R. (2000). High school career and technical education for the first decade of the 21st century. *Journal of Vocational Education Research*, 25(2), 155-198. <https://scholar.lib.vt.edu/ejournals/JVER/v25n2/lynch.html>
- McGrath, S., Akoojee, S., Gewer, A., Mabizela, M., Mbele, N., & Roberts, J. (2006). An examination of the vocational education and training reform debate in Southern Africa. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 36(1), 85-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057920500382655>
- McGrath, S., Ramsarup, P., Zeelen, J., Wedekind, V., Allais, S., Lotz-Sisitka, H., Monk, D., Openjuru, G., & Russon, J. A. (2020). Vocational education and training for African development: A literature review. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 72(4), 465-487. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2019.1679969>
- Mondoñedo, R. (2019). Assessment of the effectiveness of K-12 curriculum implementation in selected elementary schools in the Division of Rizal: Basis for policy recommendation. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2C). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/5470>
- Rahman, I. (2010). *Students' perceptions of effectiveness of hospitality curricula and their preparedness* (Master's thesis, University of Massachusetts Amherst). <https://scholarworks.umass.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1604&context=theses>
- Robinson, J. P. (2000). What are employability skills. *The Workplace*, 1(3), 1-3. https://www.middletowncityschools.com/media/user/resources/Information_Grade9_EmployabilitySkills.pdf
- Saterfiel, T. H., & McLarty, J. R. (1995). *Assessing employability skills*. ERIC Digest. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED391109.pdf>
- Shafie, L. A., & Nayan, S. (2010). Employability awareness among Malaysian undergraduates. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(8), 119-123. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v5n8p119>
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2010). *The TVET glossary of terms* (4th ed.). Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. https://unevoc.unesco.org/forum/TESDA_TVETGlossaryofTerms_%204thEd.pdf
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2014). *Training regulations: Cookery NC II: Tourism sector (Hotel and restaurant)*. Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. <https://www.tesda.gov.ph/Downloadables/TR%20Cookery%20NC%20II.pdf>
- Tran, T. T. (2016). Enhancing graduate employability and the need for university-enterprise collaboration. In M. Harvey & A. Rowe (Eds.), *WIL 2020: Pushing the boundaries – Proceedings of the 2016 ACEN National Conference* (pp. 9-13). Australian Collaborative Education Network Limited. <https://doi.org/10.21153/jtlge2016vol7no1art598>
- Tullao Jr, T., Cabuay, C. J., & Hofileña, D. (2015). *Establishing the linkages of human resource development with inclusive growth* (No. 2015-13). PIDS Discussion Paper Series. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/127020>
- Uwaifo, V. O. (2010). Technical education and its challenges in Nigeria in the 21st century. *International NGO Journal*, 5(2), 40-44. <https://academicjournals.org/journal/INGOJ/article-full-text-pdf/4A4C4E640455>

- Wiebe, E., Unfried, A., & Faber, M. (2018). The relationship of STEM attitudes and career interest. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(10), em1580. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/92286>
- Woyo, E. (2013). Challenges facing technical and vocational education and training institutions in producing competent graduates in Zimbabwe. *Open Journal of Education*, 1(7), 182-189. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314840830_Challenges_Facing_Technical_and_Vocational_Education_and_Training_Institutions_in_Producing_Compentent_Graduates_in_Zimbabwe
- Zinser, R. (2003). Developing career and employability skills: A US case study. *Education+ Training*, 45(7), 402-410. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400910310499974>
- Zinser, R. (2015). Analysis of VET in Ukraine since the Soviet era. *Education+ Training*, 57(6), 685-700. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-09-2014-0114>